

Interface properties between a steel pre-stressing strand and an epoxy matrix.

J. Van Vooren¹, B. Van Vooren², D. Van Hemelrijck¹,

¹*Free University of Brussel, Dept. of Mechanics of Materials and Constructions,
Pleinlaan 2, 1050 Brussels, Belgium.*

²*Dywidag-Systems International nv
Industrieweg 25 - B3190 Boortmeerbeek*

SUMMARY: The mechanical properties of the interface between a steel pre-stressing strand and an epoxy matrix as used in a combined wedge-bond anchorage were studied. This type of anchorage transfers the loads between the bridge deck and the pylons. As for the fiber-matrix interface in composite materials the pull-out test was used to characterise the interface behaviour. The influence of the bondlength on important characteristics as for instance initial debonding and the pull-out force was investigated

KEYWORDS: Interface, pre-stressing strand, pull-out test, gradual debonding

INTRODUCTION

During the last two decades quite a few stay cable bridges have been built (Pont de Normandy, Puente del Alamillo, Cap Shui Moon). The main reason for this is the increasing demand for bridges with greater spans and acceptable erection costs combined with aesthetic structural hi-tech. A stay cable bridge mainly consists of three parts: the bridge deck which has to be supported, the pylon(s) and the stay cables, which transfer the loads (dead weight, wind, traffic,...) acting on the bridge deck to the pylon(s). To connect the stay cables to the bridge deck and the pylon, three types of anchorage's can be used: bond only, wedge only or combined wedge-bond anchorages. The first type is only applied when the loads to be transferred are very low. Wedge-only type anchorage's can transfer very high loads but, due to the dynamic loads, have the disadvantage to be very sensitive to fretting corrosion in the wedges. A combined wedge-bond anchorage prevents this fretting corrosion as an important part of the dynamic loads kept away of the wedges. In fact designers would like the wedges to take all the static loads and the bond to take all the dynamic loads. While this principle can generally be agreed upon qualitatively, it is much more difficult to define it quantitatively. In fact, the load transfer mechanism in such a combined wedge-bond anchorage has to our knowledge never been studied in detail.

Although in real live a single bond-socket may contain multiple pre-stressing strands, in this study, for simplicity the load transfer mechanism between a single strand (type 7S 1670/1860

6.9) with a diameter of 6.9mm and epoxy (DYWIPOX SVG) bond material was investigated. Figure 1 shows a bondsocket with a single pre-stressing strand.

Figure 1 Bondsocket with pre-stressing strand.

THEORY

As we found no references studying the interface behaviour between a pre-stressing strand and epoxy matrix, only references investigating the analogous situation of the interaction between fiber and matrix in composite material systems were used. Pull-out tests are used to determine the interface characteristics. Cox [1] studied the elastic load transfer using a shear lag model. Greszczuk [2] adapted this model for the pull-out of a single fiber. The effects of gradual debonding and friction were added by Lawrence [3] and Bartos [4], [5] who described the different phenomena's occurring during a pull-out test. In fact, when plotting the force versus the displacement during a pull-out test of a single strand we obtain the curve shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 Typical pull-out curve after Bartos [4]

At T_q initial debonding occurs and gradually continues until T_p where we have complete debonding and friction takes over, due to mechanical interlocking we may obtain a higher load T_{i1} before final failure. In zone I we have elastic behaviour and a perfect bonding between the strand and the epoxy. In zone II gradual debonding is observed and the influence of friction is increasing. Mechanical interlocking and friction prevent the strand being pulled-out from the epoxy in zone III.

EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The material parameters of the pre-stressing strand and the epoxy were measured using a conventional 100KN Instron (4505) tension testbench. Five single strands were tested. In order to determine the tensile properties of the epoxy, flat specimen with a thickness of 4mm and a width of 17 mm were prepared and cured for three days at 50°C. Compression of small prisms (20mmx20mmx50mm) yielded the properties of the epoxy in compression.

The interface properties between the strand and the epoxy were measured using cylindrical specimens with an embedded strand. The pull-out configuration is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Pull-out configuration

Beside the load and the crosshead displacement, five additional LVDT's (cf. figure 3) were used to monitor the displacement of the strand at the loaded and unloaded side.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The averaged material properties of a single pre-stressing strand (type 7S 1670/1860 6.9) are given in table 1.

Table 1. Material properties of the pre-stressing strand

Pre-stressing Strand	Stiffness	Poisson's ratio	Failure strength
type 7S 1670/1860 6.9	203 GPa	0.30	>1860 MPa

The epoxy Dywipox SVG was tested in tension and in compression. The results are shown in table 2.

Table 2. . Material properties of the pre-stressing strand

Epoxy matrix	Tension		Compression	
	Stiffness	Poisson's ratio	Stiffness	Poisson's ratio
Dywipox SVG	3850 MPa	0.37	4500 MPa	0.38

The properties of the interface between the strand and the epoxy were investigated using cylindrical specimens of epoxy with an embedded strand. An important parameter controlling the macroscopic interface behaviour is certainly the bondlength. The influence of the bondlength was investigated using the cylindrical specimens with a varying bondlength, in increments of 14mm, from 14mm to 152mm. Three specimens of each bondlength were tested. In all the load-displacement curves (cf. Fig.4) a kink corresponding to the initial debonding force T_q and except for a bondlengths $<55\text{mm}$ a pull-out force T_p lower than T_{II} was observed.

Figure 4: The pull-out force T in function of the strand displacement for different bondlengths. In figure 5 the pull-out force T_p is plotted as a function of the bondlength. As can be noticed we obtain a linear relation and the critical bondlength at which the strand will fail was calculated to be 327mm. The slope of the regression line yields the instantaneous frictional shear flow, $q_f=158\text{ N/mm}$.

Figure 5: The pull-out force T_p as a function of the bondlength L .

The initial debonding force T_q as a function of the bondlength L is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: The initial debonding force T_q as a function of the bondlength L .

The initial debonding force T_q as defined by Bartos [5], is given by equation (1):

$$T_q = \frac{Q}{b_2} \tanh b_2 L \quad \text{with} \quad b_2 = \left[G_m \frac{A_f E_f + A_m E_m}{A_f E_f A_m E_m} \right]^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where Q is the maximum shear flow.

For $L \gg$ we have $\tanh \beta_2 L = 1$ and consequently the ratio Q/β_2 equal to 2460N. As the equation yielding β_2 is only valid for cylindrical fibers, β_2 was determined such that the curve representing eq. (2) became tangential to the curve, $T=1816+158L$, of figure 4. This condition is fulfilled for $\beta_2=0.553$ and consequently the maximum shear flow $Q=1360\text{N/mm}$.

Figure 7 gives the analytical representation of the pull-out tests. We notice that the minimum bondlength in order to observe the gradual debonding is equal to 3.15mm. For bondlengths $L < 3.15\text{mm}$, instantaneous catastrophic debonding will occur.

Figure 7: Analytical representation of the pull-out test.

If we plot the residual load capacity due to friction T_{fr} as a function of the bondlength L we obtain figure 8. The slope of the regression line, 152 N/mm, is in good agreement with the instantaneous frictional shear flow $q_f=158$ N/mm.

Figure 8: The residual force T_{fr} as a function of the bondlength L .

In figure 9 the difference between T_{il} and T_{fr} is plotted as a function of the bondlength. As can be noticed, we obtain a frictional behaviour after complete debonding of the strand and the epoxy.

Figure 9: $T_{il} - T_{fr}$ as a function of the bondlength L

The slip Δ_{deb} of the strand in the epoxy matrix at loaded side may be calculated using eq. (2):

$$\Delta_{deb} = \frac{\Delta_1 + \Delta_2}{2} - \frac{Tl_c}{EA} - \frac{\Delta_3 + \Delta_4}{2} \quad (2)$$

where Δ_1 and Δ_2 are the displacements of the strand at the loaded side, Δ_3 and Δ_4 the displacements of the strand, due to elastic deformation of the epoxy, at the unloaded side and the second term on the right hand side of eq. (2) the elastic deformation of the unbonded strand ($l_c=80\text{mm}$). In figure 10 the load T is given as a function of Δ_{deb} for different bondlengths. For lower load levels $T < T_q$ no slip is observed and the load transfer is elastic. However, at higher loads gradual debonding becomes obvious.

Figure 10: The tensile load T in function of Δ_{deb} for different bondlengths

When gradual debonding (cf. Figure 11) is occurring, we have a load transfer due to friction along the debonded length s equal to $q_f \cdot s$ with $q_f = 158\text{N/mm}$ the instantaneous friction flow. We assume the load transfer is linear between T and $T - q_f \cdot s$.

Figure 11 Pre-stressing strand partially debonded in the epoxy cylinder

At this specific moment the slip of the strand Δ_{deb} in the epoxy cylinder is given by eq. (3):

$$\Delta_{deb} = \int_0^s \epsilon dz = \frac{1}{A.E} \int_0^s [T - q_f \cdot z] dz \quad (3)$$

with ϵ the strain in the strand. The solution to this equation is a quadratic relation in s :

$$\frac{q_f}{2} \cdot s^2 - T \cdot s + A.E. \Delta_{deb} = 0 \quad (4)$$

with a discriminant $D = T^2 - 2 \cdot q_f \cdot A.E. \Delta_{deb}$.

Solving equation (4) for s , knowing that $s=0$ for $T=T_q$, yields equation (5):

$$s = \frac{T \pm \sqrt{D}}{q_f} \Rightarrow s = \frac{T - \sqrt{D}}{q_f} \quad (5)$$

In figure 12 this relation is plotted for different bondlengths. Initially debonding is rather slow (steep curve); afterwards we observe a steady debonding process, which becomes faster to the end.

Figure 12 Tensile load T in function of debonded length s for different bondlengths

CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical properties of the interface between a steel pre-stressing strand and an epoxy matrix were studied. The influence of the bondlength on important characteristics as for instance initial debonding and the pull-out force was investigated.

In practice, pre-stressing strands work at a typical load of $T_{\max} = 0.45T_{fu} \approx 24000N$.

If we consider a pre-stressing strand of 6.9mm diameter embedded in an epoxy matrix over a length $\geq 327mm$ (i.e. embedded length needed to obtain a pull-out load equal to the tensile strength of the strand), we will obtain, since $T_{\max} > T_q$, debonding over a debonded length s . The debonding process will stop when the residual force that has to be transferred by elastic bond, is equal to $T_q = 2460N$. The debonded length s is calculated as followed:

$$s = \frac{(24000 - 2460)N}{158N/mm} = 136mm$$

In figure 13 the shear flow distribution as described by Bartos [5] is shown.

Figure 13 The shear flow distribution along the interface

As can be noticed only 146mm of the total embedded length are needed to transfer the working load of the 6.9mm pre-stressing strand and the debonded zone has a length of 136mm. Thus meaning that nearly 90% of the working load is transferred by friction.

REFERENCES

1. Cox, H.L., *The elasticity and strength of paper and other fibrous materials*, Brit. J. Appl. Phys., Vol. 3, March 1952, pp. 72-79.
2. Greszczuk, L.B., *Theoretical studies of the mechanics of the fibre-matrix interface in composites*, Interfaces in composites, ASTM STP 452, 1962, pp. 42-58.
3. Lawrence, P., *Some theoretical considerations of fiber pull-out from an elastic matrix*, J. Mat. Sci., Vol. 7, 1972, pp. 1-6.
4. Bartos, P., *Review paper : Bond in fibre reinforced cements and concretes*, Int. J. Cem. Comp., Vol. 3, 3, August 1981, pp. 159-177.
5. Bartos, P., *Analysis of pull-out tests on fibres embedded in brittle matrices*, J. Mat. Sci., Vol. 15, 1980, pp. 3122-3128.
6. Jones R.M. 1975. *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, International Student Edition, MacGraw-Hill Kogakusha Ltd, Tokyo
7. Bowling J., and Groves G.W. 1979. *The debonding and pull-out of ductile wires from a brittle matrix*. Journal of materials science 14, 431-442.